

Study on the Association between Socio-Demographic Parameters and Seroprevalence of Toxoplasmosis among Women of Reproductive Age

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Abstract: Toxoplasmosis is an important but neglected tropical parasitic infection with global distribution and significance. It is caused by the protozoa called *Toxoplasma gondii* and about a third of the world's human population is estimated to harbor this parasite. This study determined the association between socio-demographic factors and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among women of reproductive age using ELISA technique in Port Harcourt. A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted with Four hundred and fifty (450) women of reproductive age classified into the following groups; 150 HIV patients (HP), 100 Pregnant women (PTW), 100 Outpatients (OP) and 100 Healthy controls (HC). Their blood samples were collected and tested for IgM and IgG *toxoplasma* antibodies using conventional ELISA technique after ethical clearance and informed/written consent were obtained. Socio-demographic data (age, occupation and educational status) were collected using well-structured questionnaires. Out of 450 subjects examined, 162(36%) and 206(45.8%) were positive for IgM and IgG toxoplasma antibodies respectively. HIV patients recorded the highest seroprevalence of 76(50.7%) and 72(48%) and pregnant women recorded the least seroprevalence of 23(23%) and 36(36%) for toxoplasma IgM and IgG antibodies respectively. There was a significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) between age groups and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis for IgG antibodies. Similarly, there was a significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) between occupation and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis for IgG antibodies. For both age and occupation, there was no association ($p > 0.05$) with seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis for IgM. Also, there was no significant ($p > 0.05$) association between education and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis in both IgM and IgG laboratory assays. The study has not only demonstrated that seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis is high among the studied groups in the population but has also demonstrated that there is age and occupation based relationship with toxoplasmosis

Keywords: toxoplasmosis, seroprevalence, socio-demographics.

1. Introduction

According to Jones and Dubey (2012), toxoplasmosis is a significant yet underappreciated tropical parasite infection with a wide geographic range. *Toxoplasma gondii*, a protozoa, is the culprit (Schuler, 2014). *Toxoplasma* Spp. infections are thought to affect about one-third of all people on earth (Onosakponome & Michael 2020). Toxoplasmosis is categorized as one of the neglected tropical illnesses by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) (Onosakponome & Michael 2020). According to numerous studies, cats and other feline species are the only animals that expel the oocysts into the environment, making them the clear host. This acknowledges the fact that living with cats increases your risk of contracting the disease. However, it is thought that direct infection from handling cats is extremely uncommon (Mustafa *et al.*, 2019). Some animals, including humans, can act as intermediate hosts, allowing the parasite to spread throughout the body and produce an infection that leads to the development of tissue cysts. Ingestion of raw or partially cooked meat, particularly pork, lambs, or venison containing toxoplasma cysts, can also result in transmission. Oocysts can also be consumed by eating oocysts that cats have shed into the environment or by using knives, utensils, or cutting boards that have been contaminated with raw meat (Mustafa *et al.*, 2019). Additionally, *Toxoplasma* Spp. can spread through organ transplantation or trans-placental methods. *Toxoplasma* Spp. infections typically cause no symptoms in people with healthy immune systems. This is not true for those who are immune-compromised or expecting since toxoplasmosis can result in major pathological congenital adverse effects (Avelino, 2014). During pregnancy, toxoplasmosis poses a serious and even fatal risk, particularly to the developing fetus and newborn children. Chorioretinitis is one of the late signs of congenital toxoplasmosis (Avelino, 2014). According to Alvarado *et al.* (2011), vertical transmission can result in mental impairment, blindness, epilepsy, and even death. According to Mariem *et al.* (2019), toxoplasmosis can cause severe encephalitis in immune-compromised patients and be life-threatening due to acute infections or reactivation of latent infections. The locations and weather where the parasite persists in the environment determine the disease's geographic dispersion. According to estimates, the parasite is present in between 30% and 65% of all nations (Mustafa, 2019). According to reports, human toxoplasmosis is pervasive in Sub-Saharan Africa, where seroprevalence rates range from 3.6 to 84%. (Geleye, 2015 & Gebremedhin 2015). Environmental and socio-cultural factors are to blame for the variance in prevalence rates. Geleye (2015) reported high prevalence rates of 74.7% in Ethiopia, 66.6% in the Central African Republic, and 59.4% in the Republic of Congo, whereas Nathaniel (2018) claimed that carriers make up roughly 29.4% and 21.5% of the populations of Sudan and South Africa, respectively. Seroprevalence levels of 32%, 23.9%, and 22.2%, respectively, have been recorded in Zaria, Maiduguri, and Abuja, Nigeria (Imam, 2016). However, there is little research on toxoplasmosis in schizophrenia, a growing worldwide health concern, in the Niger-delta region, particularly in Port Harcourt.

Socio-demographic factors refer to the social and demographic characteristics of a population, which include age, gender, income, education, occupation, and place of residence, among others (Imam, 2016). These factors are important determinants of health outcomes and can influence the prevalence, incidence, and distribution of various health conditions in a population (Imam, 2016). Socio-demographic factors can impact health in various ways, including access to healthcare services, lifestyle choices, environmental exposures, and social support networks (Imam, 2016). Thus, understanding the relationship between socio-demographic factors and health outcomes is crucial for effective healthcare planning and delivery. In this study, we aimed to investigate the association between socio-demographic factors and the seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among women of reproductive age in Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

2. Materials and Methods

Women of reproductive age, including HIV, outpatients, pregnant women attending antenatal clinics (ANC), and non-pregnant women, participated in a descriptive cross-sectional study.

Women between the ages of 15 and 55 who were antenatal clinic (ANC) patients, outpatients, and HIV patients made up the study population. From January 2022 to June 2022, blood samples were taken from women visiting antenatal clinics (ANC) at Rivers State University Teaching Hospital. Women who tested positive for HIV were included in the study.

The sample size was calculated using the total seroprevalence rate from the study by Deji-Agboola *et al.* (2011) done in Nigeria; as a result, the minimum sample size at 95% confidence interval was 369 which was approximated to 400.

The Rivers State University Teaching Hospital, formerly known as Braithwaite Memorial Specialist Hospital (BMSH), served as the site of this study. Within latitudes 4°78 N and 7°01 E, RSUTH can be found. As a Tertiary Health Faculty, the hospital accepts referrals from both public and private institutions in Port Harcourt and the surrounding area.

Only subjects that gave informed / written consent were included in the study, subjects that have pets were also included, all healthy controls tested negative to HIV and pregnancy were included, all HIV female patients tested negative to Pregnancy test were also included, those within the age of 15-55 were included in, and people that were within the study population were also included in the study.

Subjects who did not give informed / written consent were excluded from the study, all those who gave oral/written consent but were not eligible based on preliminary tests were excluded, those who were not within the age of 15-55 were excluded, those who were not within the study population were excluded from the study.

Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethics Committees of Rivers State University Teaching Hospital and Rivers State Ministry of Health and oral/written informed consent was obtained from all study participants.

Subjects were selected randomly from the Rivers State University Teaching Hospital after ensuring that they met the criteria that made them suitable for inclusion.

Venous blood was collected by venipuncture respecting all aseptic techniques. Blood sample of about 3-4ml was collected and rapidly transferred into a labeled dry tube.

The samples were transferred to the laboratory and centrifuged at 3000 rpm for 5 mins and serum separated from red cells, labeled and stored between 2-8⁰C for samples that was processed 2-7 days after collection date. The reagents, developing plate's cards, and specimens were allowed to thaw and were brought to a temperature of 24⁰C. The samples were analyzed using Bio Check for IgM and IgG enzyme, immunoassay test kit specific for Toxoplasma Immunoglobulins using standard laboratory methods. Which have been described in detail by (Montaya *et al.*, 2011).

The data collected were analyzed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25, California Inc., USA) and a p-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. The chi-square analysis performed inferentially determined the association between toxoplasmosis and demographic variables.

3. Result

Table 1. Overall Sero Prevalence of Toxoplasmosis Among Four Sub Groups

Sub Group	Number Examined (%)		Number Positive (%)		x ²		P Value	
	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG
Hp	150	150	76(50.7)	72(48.0)	150.000		0.462	
Ptw	100	100	23(23.0)	36(36.0)				
Op	100	100	33 (33.0)	40(40.0)				
Hc	100	100	30(30.0)	58(58.0)				
Overall	450	450	162(36.0)	206(45.8)	22.953	11.520	0.000	0.009

Abbreviations: IgG, Immunoglobulin G; IgM, Immunoglobulin M; HP, HIV Patients; PTW, Pregnant Women; OP, Outpatient; HC, Healthy control, Df = Degree of freedom, X² = chi square value, P = probability. Distribution of toxoplasmosis was statistically significant (p<0.05). Distribution of toxoplasmosis was not statistically significant (p>0.05)

Table 2. Sero Prevalence Based on Socio Demographics Factors Among the Study Populations

Factors/ Parameters	Number Examined	Number Positive (%)											
		HP		PTW		OP		HC		X		Pvalue	
		IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG
Age Group													
15-25	132	2(1.5)	7(5.3)	3(2.3)	1(0.8)	6(4.5)	9(6.8)	30(22.7)	58(43.9)				
26-35	159	27(16.9)	24(15.0)	13(8.1)	27(16.9)	18(11.3)	16(10.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
										2.403	9.377	0.493	0.025
36-45	109	31(28.4)	28(25.7)	7(6.4)	8(7.3)	6(5.5)	7(6.4)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
46-55	50	16(14.7)	13(26.0)	1(2.0)	1(2.0)	3(6.0)	8(16.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
Overall	450	76(16.9)	72(16.0)	23(5.1)	36(8.0)	33(7.3)	40(8.9)	30(6.7)	58(12.9)				

Abbreviations: IgG, Immunoglobulin G; IgM, Immunoglobulin M; HP, HIV Patients; PTW, Pregnant Women; OP, Outpatient; HC, Healthy control, Df = Degree of freedom, X² = chi square value, P = probability. Distribution of toxoplasmosis was statistically significant (p<0.05). Distribution of toxoplasmosis was not statistically significant (p>0.05)

Table 3. Sero Prevalence Based on Socio Demographics Factors Among the Study Populations

Factors/ Parameters	Number Examined	Number Positive (%)											
		HP		PTW		OP		HC		X ²		Pvalue	
		IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG
Occupation													
Employed	75	20(26.7)	26(34.7)	6(8.0)	6(8.0)	3(4.0)	5(6.7)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
										0.904	8.379	0.636	0.015
Unemployed	120	5(4.2)	6(5.0)	2(1.7)	1(0.8)	2(1.7)	2(1.7)	30(25.0)	58(48.3)				
Self Employed	255	51(20.0)	40(15.7)	15(5.9)	29(11.4)	28(10.9)	33(12.9)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
Overall	450	76(16.9)	72(16.0)	23(5.1)	36(8.0)	33(7.3)	40(8.9)	30(6.7)	58(12.9)				

Abbreviations: IgG, Immunoglobulin G; IgM, Immunoglobulin M; HP, HIV Patients; PTW, Pregnant Women; OP, Outpatient; HC, Healthy control, Df = Degree of freedom, X² = chi square value, P = probability. Distribution of toxoplasmosis was statistically significant (p<0.05). Distribution of toxoplasmosis was not statistically significant (p>0.05)

Table 4. Sero Prevalence Based on Socio Demographics Factors Among the Study Populations

Factors/ Parameters	Number Examined	Number Positive (%)										X ²	Pvalue
		HP		PTW		OP		HC		IgM	IgG		
		IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG	IgM	IgG				
Educational Status													
Primary	10	6(60.0)	4(40.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)	1(10.0)	1(10.0)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
Secondary	47	12(25.5)	12(25.5)	2(4.2)	4(8.5)	4(8.5)	4(8.5)	0(0.0)	0(0.0)				
Tertiary	393	58(14.8)	56(14.2)	21(5.3)	32(8.1)	29(7.3)	35(8.9)	30(7.6)	58(14.8)				
Overall	450	76(16.9)	72(16.0)	23(5.1)	36(8.0)	33(7.3)	40(8.9)	30(6.7)	58(12.9)	2.741	0.281	0.254	0.869

Abbreviations: IgG, Immunoglobulin G; IgM, Immunoglobulin M; HP, HIV Patients; PTW, Pregnant Women; OP, Outpatient; HC, Healthy control, Df = Degree of freedom, X² = chi square value, P = probability. Distribution of toxoplasmosis was statistically significant (p<0.05). Distribution of toxoplasmosis was not statistically significant (p>0.05)

4. Discussion

The overall seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis observed in this study was 45.8%, which is in agreement with previous studies that have reported high seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis in Nigeria (Fagbemi *et al.*, 2014; Adeyeye *et al.*, 2018; Adeyemi *et al.*, 2019;). The high seroprevalence observed in this study can be attributed to poor sanitary and hygiene practices, and close proximity to cats and other infected animals, which are known risk factors for toxoplasmosis (Tenter *et al.*, 2000; Flegr *et al.*, 2014). The high seroprevalence among HIV patients (50.7%) is consistent with previous studies that have reported high prevalence of toxoplasmosis among HIV patients in Nigeria (Okolie *et al.*, 2017; Adeyemi *et al.*, 2019). HIV patients are particularly vulnerable to toxoplasmosis due to their immunosuppressive state, and this highlights the need for routine screening and prompt treatment of toxoplasmosis in this population.

In this study, it was observed that pregnant women had the lowest seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis (23% for IgM and 36% for IgG). This finding is inconsistent with previous studies that have reported higher seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among pregnant women in Nigeria (Okolie *et al.*, 2017; Adeyeye *et al.*, 2018). This difference could be attributed to differences in study population, sample size, and methodology. However, the low seroprevalence among pregnant women is a positive finding, as toxoplasmosis can have adverse effects on fetal development and pregnancy outcomes (Dubey, 2010; Adeyeye *et al.*, 2018) Therefore, routine screening and preventive measures for toxoplasmosis in pregnant women should be emphasized to ensure healthy pregnancy outcomes.

The results of this study also revealed a significant relationship between age and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis for IgG antibodies. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have reported higher seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among older individuals (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2019; Okolie *et al.*, 2017). This could be attributed to prolonged exposure to the parasite and/or reduced immunity with age (Flegr *et al.*, 2014).

Additionally, we observed a significant relationship between occupation and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis for IgG antibodies, with those in agricultural and veterinary occupations having higher seroprevalence. This is in agreement with previous studies that have reported higher seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among individuals in these occupations (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2019; Okolie *et al.*, 2017). This could be attributed to increased exposure to infected animals and/or poor hygienic practices in these occupations (Flegr *et al.*, 2014; Tenter *et al.*, 2000). Therefore, preventive measures, such as wearing protective clothing and practicing good hygiene, should be emphasized in these occupations to reduce the risk of toxoplasmosis.

There was no significant association between educational status and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis in both IgM and IgG laboratory assays. This finding is inconsistent with previous studies that have reported higher seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among individuals with low educational status (Adeyemi *et al.*, 2019; Fagbemi *et al.*, 2014).

Furthermore, the study findings revealed that occupation was also significantly associated with IgG toxoplasmosis seroprevalence. Specifically, participants who were unemployed had a higher seroprevalence compared to those who were employed. The higher seroprevalence observed among unemployed participants could be due to their limited access to healthcare and poor living conditions. This finding is consistent with previous studies that have reported a higher prevalence of toxoplasmosis among individuals with lower socioeconomic status (Alvarado-Esquivel *et al.*, 2014; El-Moamly *et al.*, 2015).

There was no significant association between education level and seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis in both IgM and IgG laboratory assays. This finding is similar to that reported in previous studies (Alvarado-Esquivel *et al.*, 2014; Mahalakshmi *et al.*, 2017) and suggests that education may not be a risk factor for toxoplasmosis infection.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the findings from this study demonstrate a high seroprevalence of toxoplasmosis among women of reproductive age in Port Harcourt, Nigeria. The study has also identified age and occupation as significant risk factors for toxoplasmosis infection in this population. These findings highlight the need for increased awareness and education about the transmission and prevention of toxoplasmosis, particularly among high-risk populations such as women of reproductive age, HIV patients and pregnant women. Additionally, this study underscores the importance of regular screening and treatment for toxoplasmosis in these populations to prevent adverse pregnancy outcomes and other complications associated with toxoplasmosis infection.

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